

The Chemical Biology Atlas

Table of Contents

Summary.....	2
Screenshots.....	3-7
References.....	7

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Summary

The **Chemical Biology Atlas** is an interactive online platform designed to facilitate the exploration of biological activities, mechanisms of action, and molecular targets associated with chemical compounds. Built on a Neo4j graph database, the Atlas enables intuitive navigation of complex relationships between molecules and biological entities. The current release is based on a harmonized library of 5,230 molecules from the Specs repurposing set, in collaboration with the Fraunhofer Institute for Translational Medicine and Pharmacology (ITMP) and Karolinska Institute (KI).¹ The database is built around publicly available annotations collected using the Chemical Annotator pipeline (https://github.com/REMEDI4ALL/chemical_annotator),¹ ensuring comprehensive and standardized data integration. The Chemical Biology Atlas offers several search capabilities, network analysis, and dynamic visualization, allowing scientists to explore interactions, mechanisms, and repurposing opportunities in chemical biology. The platform is freely accessible at <https://chembioatlas.serve.scilifelab.se/>

Screenshots

neO4j Labs Connected to Neo4j Database

Chemical Biology Atlas

[Compound search](#)
[Compound's analogues space search](#)
[Target search](#)
[Statistics](#)
[About](#)

Getting started: searching and filtering compounds

This page allows exploring annotated information on chemical compounds from the Specs repurposing set (available at ITMP and KI). To start, enter a compound's name, ChEMBL ID, or PubChem ID. Once a compound is selected, you can further filter results by target organism and confidence score to focus on the most relevant biological and experimental data for your research needs.

Search compound

Enter Name, ChEMBL ID, PubChem CID, R4...

ADENOSINE

Select organism

Select organism (Start typing to search)

Start typing...

Confidence score

Select confidence score threshold

Start typing...

Compound card

Property	Value
first_approval	1989
pref_name	ADENOSINE
withdrawn_flag	0
molecule_synonym	9-beta-d-ribofura...
max_phase	4
therapeutic_flag	1
canonical_smiles	Nc1ncnc2c1nc2[C...
standard_inchi_key	OIRDTQYFTABQO...
cbcs_id	CBK600022
molecule_chembl_id	CHEMBL477
drug_cid	60961
smiles	Nc1ncnc2(nc12)[...
cbcs_batch_id	BI1894498
broad_id	K01577834
chem_reaxn_id	CHEMBL731

Mechanism of action

Action type: AGONIST

MoA: Adenosine recepto...

Target name: ADENOSINE

Target ChEMBL_ID: CHEMBL2111329

Compound stru

Target space

Indication class

Indication_class: Cardiac: Depressant (anti-arrhythmic)

Rows per page: 5 | 1-1 of 1

MeSH space

EFO space

Target organism

Assay/target annotation

com...	ChE...	Pub...	R4A...	CBK...	smil...	assa...	assa...	stan...	stan...	pch...	Doc...
A...	CH...	60...	R4...	CB...	Nc...	F	PU...	EC...	nM	6.12	
A...	CH...	60...	R4...	CB...	Nc...	B	Dis...	Ki	nM	8	10...
A...	CH...	60...	R4...	CB...	Nc...	B	Bi...	Ki	nM	8.3	10...
A...	CH...	60...	R4...	CB...	Nc...	F	Ag...	EC...	nM	6.51	10...
A...	CH...	60...	R4...	CB...	Nc...	F	Co...	IC50	nM	6.16	10...
A...	CH...	60...	R4...	CB...	Nc...	F	Ag...	EC...	nM	6.54	10...
A...	CH...	60...	R4...	CB...	Nc...	F	Ag...	IC50	nM	8.94	10...
A...	CH...	60...	R4...	CB...	Nc...	B	Inh...	Ki	nM	8.29	10...
A...	CH...	60...	R4...	CB...	Nc...	B	Inh...	Ki	nM	6.09	10...
A...	CH...	60...	R4...	CB...	Nc...	F	Ag...	EC...	nM	6.16	10...

Average pchembl

Target distribution

Assay distribution

Assay	Count	target_organism
PUBCHEM_BIOASSAY...	1	
Displacement of [3H]R...	1	Rattus norvegicus
Binding affinity for Ade...	1	Rattus norvegicus
Agonist activity at hum...	1	Homo sapiens
Compound was evaluat...	1	Homo sapiens
Agonist activity at hum...	1	Homo sapiens
Agonist activity at hum...	1	Homo sapiens
Inhibition of [3H]-CHA ...	1	Rattus norvegicus
Inhibition of CA200645...	1	Homo sapiens
Agonist activity at hum...	1	Homo sapiens
Binding affinity to hum...	1	Homo sapiens
Binding affinity to hum...	1	Homo sapiens
Coronary vasoactivity in...	1	Canis lupus familiaris
Affinity for Adenosine ...	1	Rattus norvegicus
Blockade of Adh2 in hum...	1	Homo sapiens

Target classification

Path: levels | Value: value

Note: To view the actual structure of a selected compound, simply click on the compound node in the Target Space window. The structure will not be displayed automatically when you select a compound.

Chemical Biology Atlas

Compound search | **Compound's analogues space search** | Target search | Statistics | About

Exploring the compound's analogues space

This page enables users to explore the chemical and biological landscape of analogues related to a selected compound in the Compound search page. After choosing a compound in the Compound Search page, you can filter analogues by chemical similarity, target organism, and confidence score results.

Note

To view the actual structure of the query compound, simply click on its node in the "Target space" window on the Compound Search page. To display the structure of an analogue, click on the corresponding compound node in any graph window. Please note that structures are not shown automatically when a compound is selected—clicking is required to reveal them.

Similarity threshold

Show analogs by Tanimoto similarity
Start typing...

Select organism

Select organism (Start typing to search)
Homo sapiens

Confidence score

Select confidence score threshold
Start typing...

Query

Analogue

Target space by chemical similarity

MeSH space by chemical

Compound: Mesh_Head...
pref_name name

EFO space by chemical

Compound: EFO_Term...
pref_name name

Analogues space

ChE...	Pub...	R4A...	CBK...	smil...	Tc	cid	assa...	assa...	stan...	stan...	pch...	co
CHL_21...	R4...	CB...	Nc...	1	21...	B	Inh...	IC50	nM	7.21		
CHL_10...	R4...	CB...	CN...	0.6...	10...	B	Inh...	Ki	nM	8.03		
CHL_65...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	65...	F	Cy...	IC50	nM	6.7		
CHL_65...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	65...	F	Cy...	IC50	nM	6.58		
CHL_65...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	65...	F	Co...	IC50	nM	6.82		
CHL_65...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	65...	F	Co...	IC50	nM	6.4		
CHL_89...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	89...	B	Bl...	Ki	nM	6.75		
CHL_89...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	89...	B	Bl...	Ki	nM	6.19		
CHL_89...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	89...	B	Dis...	Ki	nM	8.55		
CHL_89...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	89...	B	Bl...	Ki	nM	7.72		
CHL_89...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	89...	B	Aff...	Ki	nM	7.06		
CHL_89...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	89...	B	Inh...	Ki	nM	6.92		
CHL_89...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	89...	B	Bl...	Ki	nM	8.86		
CHL_89...	R4...	CB...	Oj...	0.6...	89...	F	Co...	EC...	nM	7.6		

Rows per page: 25 | 1-25 of 5000

Analogues target space

c2.compou...	Tc	target_unip...	target_organ...
R4A_000...	0.647	P35869	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.579	Q8TCU5	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.486		
R4A_000...	0.328	P11309	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.328	P68400	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.328	Q13627	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.328	P49761	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.328	O43293	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.328	Q9Y463	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.328	Q9P1W9	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.328	P68400	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.328	P48729	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.328	P68400	Homo sap...
R4A_000...	0.328	Q9Y463	Homo sap...

Rows per page: 25 | 1-25 of 5000

Analogues MoA space

Compound: Target...
pref_name target_chemblId

Chemical Biology Atlas

Compound search Compound's analogues space search **Target search** Statistics About

Exploring the target compound space

This page focuses on investigating the landscape of compounds associated with a selected biological target. To start, enter a target's name, ChEMBL or UniProt IDs. Once a target is selected, you can further filter results by target organism and confidence score to focus on the most relevant biological and experimental data for your research needs. The Similarity threshold lets you adjust the level of structural similarity when displaying analogues of compounds associated with your selected target, enabling focused or broader analysis of chemical diversity. Alternatively, the Select specific compound module, allows to focus on a particular compound from the list of those associated with your selected target.

Search target

Enter Name, ChEMBL ID, UniProt, or description

Select organism

Select organism | Start typing to search

Similarity threshold

Show analogues by | Iannotti similarity

Select specific compound

Select a compound associated with your selected target

Confidence score

Select confidence score threshold

Compounds annotation

target_ta...	targeta...	ChEMBL...	PubChe...	R4A_id	CBK_id	smiles	assay_ty...	assay_de...	standard...	standard...chembl...	
Adeno...	Rattus ...	CHEM...	69178...	R4A_0...	CBK29...	O[C@H]...	B	Bindin...	Ki	nM	6.94
Adeno...	Rattus ...	CHEM...	64627...	R4A_0...	CBK30...	O=C1C...	B	Bindin...	Ki	nM	6.42
Adeno...	Rattus ...	CHEM...	64627...	R4A_0...	CBK30...	O=C1C...	B	Bindin...	Ki	nM	6.29
Adeno...	Rattus ...	CHEM...	64627...	R4A_0...	CBK30...	O=C1C...	B	Bindin...	Ki	nM	6.42
Adeno...	Rattus ...	CHEM...	8974...	R4A_0...	CBK60...	O[C@H]...	B	Bindin...	Ki	nM	7.2

Rows per page: 5 ▾ 1-5 of 89 < >

Target card

Property	Value
target_pref_name	Adenosine A2 receptor
target_organism	Rattus norvegicus
Description	Adenosine A2 receptor
protein_hierarchy	Membrane receptor > Family A ...
target_chembl_id	CHEMBL2094117

Rows per page: 5 ▾ 1-5 of 12 < >

Target organism

Target_organism
Rattus norvegicus
Homo sapiens

Rows per page: 5 ▾ 1-2 of 2 < >

EFO Space

MeSH Space

Compound space

Compound-analogue space

Chemical Biology Atlas

Compound search Compound's analogues space search Target search **Statistics** About

Dashboard summary: statistics view

Statistical overview of compounds and their biological context. All data shown include results from functional and binding assays with a pChEMBL value of 6 or higher, without applying any confidence score filtering.

Summary

Category: Metric Value: Count

Maximum phase of development distribution

Category: Max_phase Value: count

Chemical similarity relationships

13,579,866

Withdrawn

Category: Withdrawn Value: count

Confidence score distribution

Category: Metric Value: Count

Distinct assays per confidence score

Category: Metric Value: Count

Distinct targets per confidence score

Category: Metric Value: Count

Therapeutic flag

Category: Therapeutic_flag Value: count

Number of documents/year

Category: Year Value: UniqueDocuments

Target count

Target name	Count
Unchecked	5,621
Plasmodium falciparum	4,005
Human immunodeficiency virus 1	3,753
NON-PROTEIN TARGET	2,018
Epidermal growth factor recept...	1,486

Rows per page: 5 1-5 of 3350

Target organism count

Target organism	Count
Homo sapiens	2,634
Rattus norvegicus	361
Mus musculus	306
NA	230
Bos taurus	63

Rows per page: 5 1-5 of 318

Number of related targets per compound

Compound	Number of distinct targets
CHEMBL53463	713
CHEMBL65	626
CHEMBL252164	606
CHEMBL1879463	551
CHEMBL888	514

Rows per page: 5 1-5 of 3194

Number of related targets grouped by target hierarchy per compound

Compound	Target hierarchy	Number of distinct targets by hierarchy
CHEMBL20	Enzyme > Lyase	37
CHEMBL39	Membrane receptor > Family A G protein-coupled receptor > ...	30
CHEMBL12	Ion channel > Ligand-gated ion channel > GABA-A receptor	28
CHEMBL17	Enzyme > Lyase	26
CHEMBL18	Enzyme > Lyase	25

Rows per page: 5 1-5 of 10195

Number of compounds per target hierarchy

Target hierarchy	Number of compounds
Enzyme	1,581
Membrane receptor	1,106
Ion channel	393
Transporter	281
Transcription factor	235

Rows per page: 5 1-5 of 15

Number of compounds per MeSH heading

MeSH heading	Number of unique compounds
Neoplasms	501
Breast Neoplasms	293
Carcinoma, Non-Small-Cell Lung	220
Cardiovascular Diseases	184
Prostatic Neoplasms, Castration-Resistant	177

Rows per page: 5 1-5 of 1594

Number of compounds per EFO term

EFO term	Number of unique compounds
neoplasm	402
breast cancer	273
cancer	273
non-small cell lung carcinoma	220
cardiovascular disease	184

Rows per page: 5 1-5 of 1866

Chemical Biology Atlas

Compound search Compound's analogues space search Target search Statistics About

Welcome!

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Contacts

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References

1. J Reinshagen, B Seashore-Ludlow, Y Gadiya, AL Gustavsson, Z Tanoli, T Aittokallio, J Huchting, A Jenmalm-Jensen, P Gribbon, A Zaliani & F Ballante (2025). "From Library to Landscape: Integrative Annotation Workflows for Compound Libraries in Drug Repurposing", submitted.